

Prevalence of Stress and Neck Pain Among Accountants: A Cross-Sectional Study

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Abstract

Background: Neck pain is regarded as one of the most prevalent musculoskeletal issues globally. Accountants are particularly vulnerable due to the nature of their work, which typically involves extended periods of sitting. These job-related requirements frequently result in discomfort, reduced productivity, and, in certain instances, chronic disability. The **aim** of the study is to assess the frequency and intensity of neck pain experienced by accountants in Port Sudan and its association to stress. **Methodology:** A cross-sectional analytical study was carried out involving 301 accountants in Port Sudan. Participants were randomly chosen and evaluated using Neck Disability Index (NDI) and sociodemographic factors collected using a structured questionnaire. Microsoft excel program used to analyze data. All necessary ethical approvals were secured. **Results:** The results indicated that (58.5%) of participants worked between 7 and 9 hours each day. Only 9% of the participants are setting with correct posture. Most of the participants (77.7%) didn't undergone diagnosis for neck pain. Among those who have diagnosis history of neck pain, (61.2%) diagnosed with Neck Spondylosis. There were (59.8%) of the study participants reported work stress experience. Work stress effects the productivity of (75.1%) of the study participants. **Conclusion:** Neck spondylosis stands as the most frequent condition observed among accountants in this study. Prolonged hours at the desk with poor posture contribute to neck pain and stress, hindering productivity.

Introduction

Neck pain is a prevalent problem caused by muscle strain, improper posture, injuries, arthritis, or degenerated joints [1,2]. Studies have indicated that the prevalence of neck pain ranges from 29% to 40% globally, with certain occupational groups experiencing

rates as high as 54% to 76%. Furthermore, it ranks as the fourth most common cause of disability [3]. Neck pain can result in considerable functional impairment, impacting between 20% and 100% of an individual's capacity to carry out Activities of Daily Living (ADL), contingent upon the severity [4-6].

More Information

How to cite this article: Satti L, Abdelnour H, Alawad S, Gabrallah M, Alshiekh R. Prevalence of Stress and Neck Pain Among Accountants: A Cross-Sectional Study. Eur J Med Health Res, 2026;4(1):156-61.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2026.4(1).22

Keywords:

Neck pain,
stress,
physiotherapy,
accountants,
Sudan.

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Stress represents the body's physical, mental, and emotional response to pressures or demands arising from challenging circumstances, initiating reaction through hormones that increase alertness. Although short term stress can serve as a motivator, extended or excessive stress may adversely affect health, resulting in anxiety, sleep disturbances, and various other issues [6]. In addition, stress induces neck pain by activating the body's mechanism, resulting in extended muscle tension, particularly in the neck and shoulders [7]. This tension diminishes circulation, irritates nerves, and leads to stiffness, soreness, and headaches.

Accountants frequently experience neck discomfort due to extended periods of sitting, inadequate posture, and high stress work environments, which can result in muscle strain, headaches, and stiffness [7]. Neck pain is a frequent issue for accountants, with prevalence rates typically falling between 40% and 60% annually [8]. The accountant encounters numerous challenges during each hour of work as he engages with numbers through reading, writing, organizing, and performing calculations. In addition, accountants experience significant stress as a result of substantial workloads, stringent deadlines, the demand for complete accuracy, and the necessity to continually adjust to evolving technology and regulations.

Physiotherapy assists in pain management by targeting underlying issues such as inadequate posture, muscle weakness, and stiffness [10]. To address these complications, physiotherapy employs methods including manual therapy, specific exercises, heat and cold therapy, as well as electrotherapy [11]. The goal of physiotherapy is to enhance mobility, functionality, and overall quality of life, utilizing a holistic approach that takes into account physical, psychological, and social elements [12,13].

Sudan is a country in Africa situated in the northeastern part of the continent, and it is classified as one of the developing nations facing challenges in its health sector [14]. On the other hand, the 2023 conflict in Sudan has resulted in a significant health crisis, characterized by widespread trauma that has led to increased rates of depression [15,16]. The war has devastated healthcare systems and food security. This situation has resulted in direct exposure to violence, generating substantial psychological stress and an urgent demand for support services, which are presently inadequate. Various literatures indicate that the ongoing conflict in Sudan adversely impacts the environment in multiple ways, including the work environment [16]. Numerous professionals have abandoned their homes, while others report salary reductions. The war in Sudan has inflicted significant stress on families and society, resulting in family separations, economic downturns, and overwhelming existing support systems. This adds pressure to the efforts made by aid organizations such

as the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) to offer safe spaces and meet basic needs [16]. Individuals in high stress environments are more prone to experiencing disorders such as anxiety and post-traumatic stress disorder [17].

Therefore, this study aimed to evaluate the frequency and severity of neck pain encountered by accountants in Port Sudan and its correlation with stress.

Methodology

A cross-sectional analytical study was carried out among accountants in Port Sudan from April to September 2025 to evaluate the prevalence of neck pain and its association with demographic and occupational factors, as well as stress. The research was conducted in Port Sudan, which serves as the capital of the Red Sea State in Sudan and it is the primary seaport of the nation. The study includes accountants employed in banks, governmental institutions, and private enterprises. A convenience sampling method was employed. A total of 301 accountants took part in this study. Data were collected electronically through a questionnaire distributed via Google Form. The questionnaires were designed to consist of two parts. The first part gathered sociodemographic information, while the second part evaluated neck pain using the Neck Disability Index (NDI). The data were analyzed using the Microsoft Excel program and presented through descriptive statistics, including frequencies, tables, and graphs. Prior to participation, all participants reviewed and signed the consent form, which outlined the study objectives and assured confidentiality, as well as the right to withdraw at any time.

Results

Figure 1: Gender

Among the 301 individuals surveyed, 165 (54.8%) identified as male, while 136 (45.2%) identified as female, as illustrated in figure 1.

Table 1: Age

Age	Frequency	Percent (%)
25-34	127	42.2
35-44	82	27.2
45-54	54	17.9
55 and above	38	12.6
Total	301	100.0

Table 1 indicates that 127 participants (42.2%) fell within the age range of 25 to 34 years, 82 participants (27.2%) were aged between 35 and 44 years, 54 participants (17.9%) were in the 45 to 54 years age group, and 38 participants (12.6%) were 55 years or older.

Figure 2: Employment

As illustrated in figure 2 concerning employment, 175 individuals (58.1%) were employed in the private sector, while 126 individuals (41.9%) were employed in the public sector.

Table 2: Experience

Years of Experience in Accounting	Frequency	Percent (%)
1-5 years	68	22.6
6-10 years	139	46.2
More than 10 years	94	31.2
Total	301	100.0

Table 2 shows that most of participant 139 (46.2%) got experience from 6 to 10 years in their work. There were 94 (31.1%) of the participants got more than 10 years' experience. Finally, there were 68 (22.6%) of the participants got from 1 to 5 years work experience.

Figure 3: Working Hours

As in figure 3, The data on working hours indicated that 176 individuals (58.5%) worked between 7 and 9 hours each day, 62 individuals (20.6%) worked more than 9 hours, 51 individuals (16.9%) worked between 4 and 6 hours, and 12 individuals (4.0%) worked less than 4 hours.

Table 3: Posture

	Frequency	Percent (%)
Sitting with neck and back hunched	145	48%
Slouched sitting posture	47	16%
Leaning to one side while sitting	27	9%
Correct sitting posture at the desk (straight back)	26	9%
I'm not sure	26	9%
Sitting cross legged	21	7%
Other	9	3%
Total	301	100.0

Regarding posture, 145 (48%) sat with neck and back hunched, 47 (16%) slouched sitting posture, 27 (9%) leaned to one side, 26 (9%) maintained correct posture, 26 (9%) were unsure, 21 (7%) sat cross-legged, and 9 (3%) used other positions as in table 3.

Table 4: Pain Intensity

	Frequency	Percent (%)
No pain	48	15.9
Mild	55	18.3
Mild to moderate	37	12.3
Moderate	62	20.6
Severe	46	15.3
Very severe	53	17.6
Total	301	100.0

Table 4 shows that moderate pain was most frequent intensity with 62 (20.6%) participants at level 3. Using NDI

Table 5: Diagnosed of Neck Condition or Surgery

	Frequency	Percent (%)
Yes,	67	22.3
No	234	77.7
Total	301	100.0

A total of 67 (22.3%) reported diagnoses of neck condition or surgery, while 234 (77.7%) did not as in table 4.

Table 6: Diagnosis History of Neck

Diagnosis	Frequency	Percent (%)
Spondylosis	41	61.2%
Neck muscle spasm	4	5.9%
Disc Herniation	22	32.9%
Total	67	100.0

Among those diagnosed, conditions included Neck Spondylosis 41 (61.9%), Neck Disc Herniation 22 (32.9%), and Neck muscle spasm 4 (5.9%) as in table 5.

Table 7: Work Stress

	Frequency	Percent (%)
Yes	180	59.8
No	121	40.2
Total	301	100.0

Workplace stress was reported as a factor by 180 (59.8%) while (40.2%) didn't have work stress.

Table 8. Stress Impact Productivity

	Frequency	Percent (%)
Yes	226	75.1
No	75	24.9
Total	301	100.0

Impact on productivity was significant and 226 (75.1%) stress effects their productivity and 75 (24.9%) stress have no effect on their productivity.

Discussion

A study done by Satti et al. (2025) found that students at the National University (NU) in Sudan use their phones for over five hours daily, a significant factor contributing to neck pain, as it investigated the awareness and prevalence of Text Neck Syndrome (TNS) among students [18]. Most participants in this study work seven to nine hours daily, which increases their risk for neck pain. Moreover, only 9% of the participants in this research upheld correct posture during their working hours. Proper posture reduces

neck discomfort by keeping the ears aligned with the shoulders and spine. Addressing forward head posture decreases the strain on both the neck and spine. In other word, reducing the extra strain on the neck muscles and joints, easing tension headaches, boosting movement efficiency, and preventing chronic pain, resulting in improved overall spinal health and function. The prevalence of moderate pain was the most common experience reported by the participants in this study, indicating that a majority of individuals reported experiencing pain of a moderate intensity during the period of their involvement. Moderate neck discomfort is widespread, with research indicating substantial prevalence about 40% to 45% of moderate neck pain on the NDI [19].

Cervical discomfort poses a significant health issue in Sudan, with studies revealing a substantial incidence within specific occupational groups, including those engaged in computer based work and surgical professions [20]. The present investigation found that a few proportions of participants had received a diagnosis of a cervical condition or had undergone surgical intervention for it. More investigation needed to explore this which our current study missed. In other words, there are a need of knowing why most didn't seek diagnosis. The study of Satti et al (2025), mentioned challenges in rehabilitation consultation [18]. Among those few participants who had diagnosis, many had a previous history of Neck Spondylosis. Neck spondylosis also known as Cervical Spondylosis, is an exceedingly common ailment. It's an age-related change in the neck that impacts more than 85% of individuals over 60 [21]. Neck pain can be attributed to various medical conditions, including muscle strain, Osteoarthritis, physical injuries, herniated discs, bone spurs, Rheumatoid Arthritis, or Meningitis.

As noted previously, neck pain linked to sedentary jobs and psychological factors like stress [6,22]. In this study, workplace stress was cited as a factor by a number of participants. Moreover, pain impact on productivity was significant and many participants in this study stated that stress effects their productivity. Pain substantially diminishes productivity by impairing attention, decision making, and physical functioning, leading to missed deadlines and reduced output [22,23]. It also provokes emotional distress, including frustration and depressive symptoms, which further degrade work quality and overall well-being [6,23]. The brain's motivation system is disrupted, rendering tasks more difficult, and concomitant factors such as poor sleep, mental health concerns, and physical limitations exacerbate the overall impact [23].

Finally, the impact of neck pain significantly influences the productivity of Sudanese accountants, which is associated with the duration of working hours and improper posture. Work related stress is a primary

factor contributing to the complications associated with neck pain.

Conclusion

Neck spondylosis stands as the most frequent condition observed among accountants in this study. Prolonged hours at the desk with poor posture contribute to neck pain and stress, hindering productivity. Additional research should explore accountants' awareness of proper neck-pain rehabilitation.

Authors' Contribution

All authors participated in every phase of this study, including data collection, data analysis, manuscript writing, editing, and reviewing.

Acknowledgment

The authors express their gratitude to all participants who took part in this study. For technical support authors also would like to thank Ms. Safa Abdelnour, HR Business Partner SFL4, Amazon Service Inn, Tampa, Florida, USA.

Funding

The study did not receive any funding.

Conflict of Interest

The authors affirm that there are no conflicts of interest.

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